

Randomized audios for each rater in step 3

(Taking cycle 1 for example)

For cycle 1 (C1), denoted as 'A' here in this script, we extracted five audio files: A1, A2, A12, A18, and A20, representing 5C1. The remaining audio files for this cycle are:

```
['A3', 'A4', 'A5', 'A6', 'A7', 'A8', 'A9', 'A10', 'A11', 'A13', 'A14', 'A15', 'A16', 'A17', 'A19', 'A21', 'A22']
```

These 17 audios should be evaluated for three evaluations by three different raters, resulting in $17 \times 3 = 51$ audios in total for A.

Randomize the audios file for 5 raters to meet two conditions:

- Non-repetition: Ensuring each rater receives only one file from the same subset.
- Balanced distribution: Each rater is assigned either 10 or 11 files, ensuring an equitable workload.

follow the script in the Python environment

```
import random

# Define the items
items = ['A1', 'A2', 'A4', 'A5', 'A7', 'A8', 'A9', 'A10', 'A12', 'A13', 'A14', 'A16', 'A17', 'A18', 'A19', 'A20', 'A22']

# Define the raters
raters = ['Rater 1', 'Rater 2', 'Rater 3', 'Rater 4', 'Rater 5']

# Define a dictionary to keep track of how many times each item has been used
item_counts = {item: 0 for item in items}

# Define a function to assign items to raters
def assign_items(num_items):
    assigned_items = []
    while len(assigned_items) < num_items:
        # Shuffle the items
        random.shuffle(items)
```

```

# Try to assign an item that has only been used twice
for item in items:
    if item_counts[item] < 2:
        assigned_items.append(item)
        item_counts[item] += 1
        break

# If no item has only been used twice, assign an item that
has only been used three times
else:
    for item in items:
        if item_counts[item] < 3:
            assigned_items.append(item)
            item_counts[item] += 1
            break
return assigned_items

# Assign items to raters
rater_assignments = {}
for rater in raters:
    if rater == 'Rater 5':
        # Rater 5 gets 11 items
        assigned_items = assign_items(11)
    else:
        # Other raters get 10 items
        assigned_items = assign_items(10)
    rater_assignments[rater] = assigned_items

# Print the results
for rater, assigned_items in rater_assignments.items():
    print(f"{rater}: {' '.join(assigned_items)}")

```